

D1.4

Analysis of public engagement with H₂ via social media channels across the EU27

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Partners short names

ENVI	Parco Scientifico Tecnologico Per L'ambiente Environment Park Torino Spa
IMI	Institute for Methods Innovation
IME	Fundacion IMDEA Energia
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
CNH2	Centro Nacional Del Hidrógeno
RIGP	Regionalna Izba Gospodarcza Pomorza
CLUSTER TWEED	Cluster Tweed
BH2C	Balkanski Vodородen Klaster

Acronyms

SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
EU	European Union
H₂	Hydrogen
API	Application Programming Interfaces
SM	Social Media
FCEV	Fuel cell electric vehicle

Executive Summary

This social media analysis report provides broad coverage of the full set of EU member states (EU27), as well as analyses focusing specifically on the EU13: Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia. In addition to providing valuable information about public engagement and interest in topics related to hydrogen (H₂) energy and technology on social media, this analysis provides recommendations that will feed into planning the HYPOP project's co-creation and public engagement workshops with participants in EU13 countries (WP3).

Findings in this report reveal a mosaic of engagement levels across the EU27, with certain countries displaying a more pronounced interest in specific hydrogen energy-related topics. A mix of national initiatives or local discourse likely influenced the differences found between countries. Indeed, public interest was inclined toward the technological aspects of hydrogen, such as hydrogen fuel cells and vehicles, suggesting a curiosity and potential readiness among the public towards embracing hydrogen-based solutions. However, there was a noticeable gap in public engagement with topics related to hydrogen energy infrastructure and policies, indicating a potential area for targeted awareness and educational initiatives. Finally, socio-political factors likely substantially influenced the public's perception and engagement with hydrogen technology, with varying degrees of scepticism and enthusiasm observed across countries.

The report underscores the diverse nature of public interest in hydrogen technology across EU countries, highlighting the need for country-specific engagement strategies. Findings from this deliverable support the need to tailor these strategies to each member state's unique interests, concerns and cultural contexts.

In summary, this report offers a snapshot of current social media engagement with hydrogen technology in the EU27 and a roadmap for shaping future public-facing interactions and dialogues around hydrogen energy.

1 Introduction

Hydrogen (H₂) technology is emerging as a pivotal element in the transition towards cleaner energy sources. Understanding public engagement and sentiment towards H₂ is crucial, as public perception can substantially influence policy-making, investment decisions, and the overall success of hydrogen initiatives. This report aims to untangle the differences in public engagement and interest in hydrogen-related topics across the European Union's 27 member states (EU27), leveraging social media and Google search trends as data sources.

The relevance of this analysis stems from the integral role public opinion can play in the energy sector's evolution. As the EU strides towards ambitious decarbonisation goals, gauging public interest and concerns about H₂ is indispensable for aligning strategies with societal expectations and fostering public support. Furthermore, the analysis offers valuable insights for key players in hydrogen technology, including the energy industry, public policy, and academia.

Moreover, social media searches serve as indicators of public interest and engagement with a topic, providing real-time data that reflects the pulse of society¹. By analysing these data, we aim to uncover patterns, trends, and shifts in public discourse, offering an understanding of how H₂ is perceived across diverse cultural and linguistic contexts within the EU27 based on organically developing discussions.

This study maps social media-based public engagement with hydrogen technology and identifies drivers of interest or concern, thereby contributing to a more informed and responsive approach to advancing the hydrogen economy within the EU.

¹ cf., Jensen 2014. § Jensen, E. (2017). Putting the methodological brakes on claims to measure national happiness through Twitter: Methodological limitations in social media analytics. *PLOS ONE*. <http://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0180080> [DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0180080]

2 Methodology

Our approach includes both quantitative and qualitative social media data sources from across the EU27. From October 2023 to January 2024, **weekly searches were conducted on social media platforms** (such as Facebook, X, Reddit and YouTube) to compile a relevant dataset. During these searches, the focus was on identifying **keywords, hashtags, users and relevant discussions** on social media for further analysis.

Figure 1. Excerpt of weekly searches on social media

Date	Keywords on social media	Hashtags
Friday 13 October 2023	hydrogen fuel-based economy, hydrogen trucks, green hydrogen, hydrogen fuel cell electric vehicle, clean energy, renewable energy, H ₂ economy, hydrogen fuel cell	#NationalHydrogenDay, #cleanhydrogen,
Friday 20 October 2023	hydrogen fuel cell technology, green hydrogen, green hydrogen hub	#ClimateJustice
Friday 27 October 2023	electric cars, green hydrogen	
Friday 3 November 2023	hydrogen fuel cell vehicles, renewable energy, green hydrogen technology	#HydrogenFuture, #CleanEnergy
Friday 10 November 2023	hydrogen vehicles	
Friday 17 November 2023	green hydrogen, EU hydrogen bank, hydrogen fuel cell systems, renewable hydrogen	
Friday 24 November 2023	European Hydrogen Week 2023, greenwashing, green hydrogen, hydrogen station	
Friday 1 December 2023	renewable energy, green hydrogen, hydrogen fuel cell vehicles, hydrogen fuel	#COP28
Friday 8 December 2023	hydrogen, regulatory framework for hydrogen, hydrogen market rules, gas decarbonisation, energy security, green hydrogen, clean hydrogen, hydrogen infrastructure, hydrogen cars, hydrogen engine,	#hydrogen, #biomethane, #HydrogenWeek, #H2Europe, #EUH2Week, #H2, #COP28, #COP28UAE

In the process of compiling this social media dataset, limitations inherent to social media platforms' proprietary Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) were encountered. These platforms often impose restrictions on data access and are subject to frequent changes in policies and access permissions, which disrupted the data extraction for this study.

To address these challenges and broaden the analytical scope, Google Trends was integrated into the methodology in addition to traditional social media platforms. Google Trends compensated for the restricted access and platform-centric data of social media APIs by providing a more comprehensive view of public interest across multiple digital fronts. Unlike social media APIs, Google Trends offers

insights into the volume and nature of search queries, capturing a wider array of public interests and sentiments that may not be voiced on social media platforms.

To compile the dataset from Google Trends, the list of identified keywords was processed through Google Keyword Planner² first. This helped uncover additional pertinent search terms that may have been overlooked during the weekly searches. Keywords registering **over 5,000 average monthly searches across the EU27** were incorporated, resulting in a list of 63 search terms. These search terms can be useful for the project’s SEO strategy, attracting more visitors to the website through search engines.

Table 1. List of identified keywords

<p>hydrogen fuel cell hydrogen fuel hydrogen fuel cell price hydrogen fuel car hydrogen fuel cell vehicles hydrogen fuel price hydrogen combustion engine hydrogen automobiles hydrogen powered automobiles cars using hydrogen hydrogen fuel cell technology hydrogen fuel cell diagram hydrogen fuel cell efficiency hydrogen fuel energy hydrogen fuel generator home hydrogen refuelling stations hydrogen combustion vehicle hydrogen fuel gas station hydrogen service stations hydrogen powered cars hydrogen trucks green hydrogen</p>	<p>green hydrogen stocks green hydrogen production green hydrogen systems H₂ economy hydrogen vehicles pros and cons hydrogen vehicles eu hydrogen week eu hydrogen strategy eu hydrogen bank eu hydrogen auction eu hydrogen policy eu hydrogen funding eu hydrogen rules renewable energy systems renewable hydrogen renewable hydrogen alliance renewable hydrogen coalition renewable hydrogen production renewable hydrogen energy renewable hydrogen strategy renewable hydrogen definition</p>	<p>renewable hydrogen industry development plan green hydrogen greenwashing blue hydrogen greenwashing hydrogen market size hydrogen market price hydrogen market outlook hydrogen market growth hydrogen market value clean hydrogen clean hydrogen partnership clean hydrogen works clean hydrogen joint undertaking clean hydrogen future coalition clean hydrogen tax credit eu regulatory framework for hydrogen hydrogen cars hydrogen engine hydrogen stock eu renewable energy eu green energy</p>
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² Google Keyword Planner is a tool provided by Google Ads that offers insights on search volume. <https://ads.google.com/home/tools/keyword-planner/>

The 63 terms were then run through Google Trends. While Keyword Planner provides absolute numbers indicating the expected number of searches for keywords locally and globally, Google Trends offers data³ on relative search frequency⁴, **with the peak search volume indexed at 100**. This feature allows for effective benchmarking and comparison between different search terms or locations, offering insights into relative popularity or interest that are not apparent through absolute search volumes alone. By incorporating this tool into the search methodology, it was possible to gain a nuanced understanding of the H₂ discourse's dynamism and complexity across the EU27.

A total of **16 topics were identified** using the 63 search terms identified through Google Keyword Planner. In Google Trends, a 'topic' is a group of terms that share the same concept in any language, making them more robust for cross-linguistic analysis because they are language agnostic and account for variations and misspellings. This is especially important in the linguistically diverse EU27 context.

Table 2. List of identified topics

Hydrogen (chemical element)	Hydrogen-powered ship
Hydrogen fuel	Hydrogen-powered aircraft
hydrogen internal combustion engine	Fuel cell
Hydrogen internal combustion engine vehicle	Fuel cell vehicle
Hydrogen vehicle	Green hydrogen
Hydrogen economy	Hydrogen production
Hydrogen fuel station	European Green Deal
Hydrogen station	Hydrogen Europe

Once this initial set of topics was identified, it became necessary to refine the selection to ensure specificity to hydrogen-related discussions. Initially identified broad topics such as *hydrogen* and *fuel cell* were integral to the discourse on hydrogen energy, yet their scope extended beyond the specific focus of the study. For example, the term *hydrogen* is frequently associated with various contexts, ranging from scientific discussions on chemical properties to its use in diverse industries. Similarly, *fuel cell* technology, although relevant, is employed in multiple energy contexts not limited to H₂, such as in applications using natural gas or methanol.

To maintain the focus of the analysis, the topics of *hydrogen*, *fuel cell*, and *European Green Deal* were excluded. Only topics explicitly related to hydrogen as a renewable energy source were retained. This approach ensured that the analysis accurately reflected public engagement specifically with hydrogen energy technologies, avoiding mixing in broader or unrelated discussions.

After this initial phase of topic refinement, a country-by-country dataset was extracted from Google Trends, forming the backbone of the quantitative analysis. These datasets include the relative search frequency over the last 12 months (February 2023 - January 2024), related top topics and related top queries. After cleaning the data, it was discovered that four of the 13 topics showed no substantial

³ Identified through Google's Knowledge Graph technology, aggregating search information across Search, Google News, and YouTube.

⁴ Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location.

activity in the EU27 and EU13 countries. Ultimately, the topics *hydrogen fuel station*, *hydrogen internal combustion engine*, *hydrogen-powered ship* and *hydrogen Europe* were removed from the final list.

It is important to note that the topic of *fuel cell vehicle* was deliberately included despite the acknowledgement that not all fuel cell vehicles use H₂. This decision was made after a careful review of data extracted from Google Trends, which indicated that a significant proportion of the discourse on fuel cell vehicles is related to those powered by H₂. These vehicles play a pivotal role in advancing hydrogen energy within the automotive sector, representing a key area of public interest and technological development.

Table 3. Final list of topics

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hydrogen fuel Hydrogen internal combustion engine vehicle Hydrogen vehicle Hydrogen economy Hydrogen station 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hydrogen-powered aircraft Fuel cell vehicle Green hydrogen Hydrogen production
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To complement the insights derived from Google Trends, a content analysis was conducted on a curated selection of social media posts. These posts were carefully chosen based on multiple criteria: their relevance to the previously identified search terms or topics, the level of user engagement they garnered, their geographic representation across the EU27, the timeliness of the posts within the study period, the influence of the users who posted them, and the diversity of the content types. Each post was then meticulously analysed to further understand public sentiment and engagement with hydrogen technology.

Through this methodological approach, combining Google Trends data with targeted social media content analysis, a coherent picture was constructed of public engagement with hydrogen across the EU27, offering valuable insights into the prevailing perceptions and discussions within the region.

3 Analysis of public engagement with H₂ via social media channels across the EU27 and EU13

To facilitate the data analysis, multiple hydrogen-related topics were grouped into four pillars: **technology** (green hydrogen, hydrogen fuel), **mobility** (hydrogen internal combustion engine vehicle, hydrogen vehicle, fuel cell vehicle, hydrogen-powered aircraft), **infrastructure** (hydrogen station), and **economy and politics** (hydrogen economy, hydrogen production).

3.1 Quantitative analysis

3.1.1 Technology: EU27

The topic of *green hydrogen* was not very popular in 2023 within our social media dataset, reaching only a 4-point relative search frequency in Spain and 0 in approximately 25% of the EU27 countries.

In contrast, the topic of *hydrogen fuel* showed an increased frequency in Ireland (34) and France (20) (Figure 2). 2023 was an important year for hydrogen energy in Ireland: the first-ever National Green Hydrogen Strategy was released in July 2023, and a Joint Declaration of Intent on cooperation was signed in the field of green hydrogen with the German Federal Research Ministry.

Figure 2. Annual average relative search frequency for the topic *hydrogen fuel* across EU27 countries⁵

⁵ Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location, with the peak search volume indexed at 100.

3.1.2 Hydrogen fuel and energy topics: EU13

The topic of *hydrogen fuel* only showed substantial trend data in the Czech Republic, Estonia, Poland and Romania (Figure 3). In general, one of the top related topics was *Toyota* (and its hydrogen car, *Mirai*). During Europe’s Hydrogen Week in Brussels, Toyota showcased its fuel cell modules. It displayed the Mirai and Hilux FCEV prototype, which could explain the interest throughout the EU13 countries in this particular topic. In the case of Czechia, it showed a steady interest, probably due to the Orlen Group (a Polish petrol retailer) announcing plans to expand its network of hydrogen refuelling stations in the country.

Figure 3. Trend analysis of search frequency for the topic *hydrogen fuel* across EU13 countries⁶

The topic of *green hydrogen* was popular in Romania, Poland, Cyprus and the Czech Republic (Figure 4). The top related topics were *renewable energy*, *energy*, and *production*. Romania and Poland’s search frequency peaks in September 2023 can be attributed to the European Commission President, Ursula von der Leyen, outlining hydrogen’s key role in transforming mobility and industry sectors during a keynote speech at the Green Deal Summit in Prague in that same month. In the case of

⁶ Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location, with the peak search volume indexed at 100.

Cyprus, this peak (although not as prominent as the ones from other countries) can also be related to the Green Hydrogen in Cyprus event held in Nicosia in September 2023. Finally, Poland's peak in January 2024 can be attributed to Metacon, an international energy technology company, signing a Memorandum of Understanding with the Regional Directorate of State Forests (RDSF) in Katowice, Poland for a 5 MW green hydrogen project.

Figure 4. Trend analysis of search frequency for the topic *green hydrogen* across EU13 countries⁷

3.1.3 Hydrogen-based mobility topics: EU27

One of the most searched topics related to mobility was the *hydrogen internal combustion engine* (Figure 5). It was most searched in France (77), Spain (59) and Germany (27). In April 2023, the French government approved using hydrogen engines to retrofit special vehicles, accelerating the adoption of cleaner, greener transportation technologies by simplifying these regulations. Another major news that can explain the high levels of interest in Spain and Germany is the H2med project, a transnational initiative to interconnect the hydrogen networks of the Iberian Peninsula to Northwest Europe,

⁷ Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location, with the peak search volume indexed at 100.

enabling Europe to be supplied with affordable green hydrogen by 2030. This initiative was launched by France, Spain and Portugal, with strong support from Germany.

Figure 5. Annual average relative search frequency for the topic *hydrogen internal combustion engine* across EU27 countries⁸

A similar topic, *hydrogen vehicle*, was most searched in Denmark (100), followed by the Netherlands (41) and Ireland (34) (Figure 6). Denmark's high search frequency could be related to Everfuel, the Danish hydrogen infrastructure provider, announcing that its network of hydrogen refuelling stations would close.

⁸ Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location, with the peak search volume indexed at 100.

Figure 6. Annual average relative search frequency for the topic *hydrogen vehicle* across EU27 countries⁹

In general, topics related to *hydrogen vehicle* could suggest that European citizens are still getting acquainted with H₂ as a technology, showing a tendency towards the search for more narrow terms such as *combustion engine* to understand what they are and how they work, and not terms that could be applied to their everyday lives such as *fuel cell vehicle*, a topic that was most searched in Sweden (19), Germany (12) and Austria (10) (Figure 7). The relative search frequency in Germany can be attributed to the International Expo and Conference for the Hydrogen and Fuel Cell community held in Stuttgart in September 2023.

⁹ Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location, with the peak search volume indexed at 100.

Figure 7. Annual average relative search frequency for topic *fuel cell vehicle* across EU27 countries¹⁰

The topic of *hydrogen-powered aircraft* showed a substantial level of search frequency in several EU27 countries, with France being the country with the highest level (100) (Figure 8). This may be related to Beyond Aero, a French start-up, recently announcing its first successful flight of a hydrogen aircraft named Blériot. As for the rest of the countries, such as Germany, the Netherlands, Austria, Belgium and Ireland, this frequency can be related to other similar news, such as H2FLY, the developer of hydrogen fuel and sustainable technologies for aviation, announcing the completion of the world’s first piloted flight of a liquid hydrogen-powered electric aircraft in September 2023.

¹⁰ Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location, with the peak search volume indexed at 100.

Figure 8. Annual average relative search frequency for the topic *hydrogen-powered aircraft* across EU13 countries¹¹

¹¹ Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location, with the peak search volume indexed at 100.

3.1.4 Hydrogen-based mobility topics: EU13

In contrast, all EU13 countries showed some interest in the term *hydrogen vehicle* (Figure 9). Romania, Slovenia and Poland were the countries with the highest search frequency. For example, most countries had a peak between September and November 2023, probably related to the European Hydrogen Week, where Honda, Toyota and other car manufacturers showcased prototypes of their next-generation hydrogen-powered vehicles. Countries such as Poland showed a steady frequency by the end of 2023, probably related to the notable progress made by hydrogen vehicles in that same year.

Figure 9. Trend analysis of search frequency for the topic *hydrogen vehicle* across EU13 countries¹²

In contrast, the topic of *hydrogen internal combustion engine* only showed movement in the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Romania and Poland (Figure 10). The top related topics that were searched alongside *hydrogen internal combustion energy* were *electrical motors*, *Toyota* and *hydrogen vehicles*. In summary, 2023 saw continued interest in this technology in several countries despite no major related news.

¹² Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location, with the peak search volume indexed at 100.

Figure 10. Trend analysis of search frequency for the topic *hydrogen internal combustion engine vehicle* across EU13 countries¹³

The topic of *fuel cell vehicle* was only searched in Romania, the Czech Republic and Poland (Figure 11). As mentioned earlier, this topic refers to a specific type of hydrogen technology. The top related topics were *hydrogen*, *fuel cell* and *vehicle*. In the case of the Czech Republic, the peaks of interest could be related to the refining and petrochemical group ORLEN Unipetrol implementing a pilot operation of a low-floor electric bus with hydrogen fuel cells across the country, as well as Bosch’s plant at České Budějovice (one of the German company’s largest research and development centres in Europe) announcing that it would undergo a major transformation to focus on green hydrogen and fuel cell technology in October 2023.

¹³ Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location, with the peak search volume indexed at 100.

Figure 11. Trend analysis of search frequency for the topic *fuel cell vehicle* across EU13 countries¹⁴

It is worth noting that these two topics (*hydrogen internal combustion engine vehicle* and *fuel cell vehicle*) are more specialised since they refer to specific types of technology used by hydrogen vehicles: the former produces power through combustion, and the latter converts hydrogen into electricity. This could explain why these topics show different high search frequencies compared to the more generic topic of *hydrogen vehicle*.

Finally, the topic of *hydrogen-powered aircraft* was only searched in Hungary and Poland (Figure 12). While no major specific news was related to this topic in these two countries, two important pieces of European news coincided with the peak interest levels in March and July. The first one is related to the Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking (Clean Aviation JU) and the Clean Hydrogen Joint Undertaking (Clean Hydrogen JU) signing a Memorandum of Understanding to establish strategic cooperation on research and innovation in hydrogen-powered aviation during the Clean Aviation Annual Forum in March 2023. The second one relates to the publication of the key recommendations from the Clean Aviation and Clean Hydrogen joint workshop on H₂-powered aviation in July 2023.

¹⁴ Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location, with the peak search volume indexed at 100.

Figure 12. Trend analysis of search frequency for the topic *hydrogen-powered aircraft* across EU13 countries¹⁵

¹⁵ Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location, with the peak search volume indexed at 100.

energy company called Alexela announced that it would open the first hydrogen stations in the country. Finally, an international energy technology company called Metacon announced that it was set to supply an integrated 1MW Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) electrolyser and hydrogen refuelling station to an unnamed client in Slovakia.

3.1.7 Hydrogen economy and production topics: EU27

The topic of *hydrogen economy* was most searched in Finland (12), showing little to no interest in the rest of the EU27 countries (Figure 14). Although Finland’s search frequency is not very high, it can be related to the adoption of a resolution on hydrogen by the national government at the beginning of 2023. According to this resolution, Finland aims to become the leading European nation in the hydrogen economy value chain.

Figure 14. Annual average relative search frequency for the topic hydrogen economy across EU27 countries¹⁷

While the topic of *hydrogen production* did not present any high search frequencies (above 70), it did show activity in more EU27 countries than the previous topic (Figure 15). It was most searched in Portugal (15) and Finland (11). In the case of Portugal, this level of interest could be related to the launch of a pioneering auction for rights to sell green hydrogen for injection into the national gas grid, as well as the signing of a declaration of cooperation with Luxembourg to develop a large electrolyser project to produce renewable hydrogen at the port of Sines.

Figure 15. Annual average relative search frequency for the topic *hydrogen production* across EU27 countries¹⁸

¹⁸ Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location, with the peak search volume indexed at 100.

3.1.8 Hydrogen economy and production topics: EU13

At the EU13 level, the topic of *hydrogen economy* was not very popular. It only showed a moderate level of interest in Poland (Figure 16), with the top related topics being *energy*, *economy* and *cars*.

Figure 16. Trend analysis of search frequency for the topic *hydrogen economy* across EU13 countries¹⁹

On the other hand, the topic of *hydrogen production* was searched in several countries, with Poland, the Czech Republic and Croatia showing the highest search frequencies (Figure 17). In the case of Croatia, this could be related to Baker Hughes, an American energy company, signing a deal to collaborate on various value chain areas related to green hydrogen production. The peak in search frequency in Romania in May 2023 can be attributed to OMV Petrom, a national refinery, confirming the construction of renewable hydrogen production facilities at its Petrobrazi oil refinery. In Poland, Romania and Slovenia, people who searched for the topic of *hydrogen production* were also interested in topics such as *electrolysis*, *pyrolysis* and *photocatalysis*.

¹⁹ Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location, with the peak search volume indexed at 100.

Figure 17. Trend analysis of search frequency for the topic *hydrogen production* across EU13 countries²⁰

²⁰ Each score represents the relative volume of a query compared to the total number of searches performed over a given time and location, with the peak search volume indexed at 100.

3.2 Qualitative analysis of hydrogen technology topics in social media

A detailed qualitative analysis of a range of social media posts was conducted to gain a deeper understanding of how hydrogen technology topics are discussed among general public audiences. This analysis is aimed at complementing the results from the quantitative analysis of Google Trends data presented above.

3.2.1 Qualitative analysis methodology

The purposive sample of social media posts was based on the following criteria: the posts' relevance to the identified hydrogen technology topics, the level of user engagement, their spread across the EU27 countries, date of posting and the diversity of content types.

In the selection process, it was not possible to identify any Facebook posts that met the criteria, leading us to use X posts and Reddit threads as the main platforms included in the sample. X is known for the dynamic, real-time discussions on current issues, including technology and environmental topics, making it a valuable source for understanding public opinions and trending discussions on hydrogen technology. Reddit, while less widely used, can often host in-depth discussions and a broad range of viewpoints on specialised topics, such as hydrogen technology. Together, these platforms provide a rich source of data about public discourse, enhancing the analysis of how the EU27 perceives hydrogen technology.

3.2.2 X case study: H₂ as a decarbonisation strategy

A tweet posted by the European Commission [promoting hydrogen as a key technology for decarbonising the economy on 23 November 2023](#) (Figure 18) was followed by various replies ranging from scepticism and misinformation to political opposition and mockery, illustrating the challenges of public communication and acceptance of new technologies.

- Several replies expressed scepticism or outright dismissal of hydrogen technology. Comments like "*Lol... hydrogen bombs. No thank you*" and "*No thanks*" indicated a lack of trust or interest in the technology being promoted.
- Replies such as "*It's a red herring to distract and delay...*" and "*Hydrogen is a fraud that You're using to tax everything...*" suggest that some individuals perceived the promotion of hydrogen as misleading or as a scheme with ulterior motives, possibly linked to financial or political agendas.
- Questions like "*Renewable hydrogen... How do you 'renew' it?*" indicated a lack of understanding or misinformation regarding the production and use of green hydrogen, highlighting a need for clearer communication on how renewable hydrogen is produced.
- Some replies, such as "*Nobody needs this EU! #Dexit now!*" and responses containing hashtags like "*#WEFscam*" and "*#Nonsenseldeology*," reflected political or ideological opposition that extends beyond the topic of hydrogen, indicating broader dissatisfaction with the European Commission or related entities.

This diversity of reactions highlights the importance of addressing public concerns, clarifying misconceptions, and engaging in more effective dialogue about the role of hydrogen in the energy transition.

Figure 18. European Commission's tweet about the European Hydrogen Bank

3.2.3 X case study: Public reactions to the EU Green Deal announcement

On 3 October 2023, the European Commission tweeted about [the EU Green Deal's advantages to the industry](#) (Figure 19). The replies to this tweet showed a broad range of opinions, from outright rejection and scepticism to nuanced critiques and selective support, which highlights the complexity of public reception to policies like the Green Deal and the importance of addressing diverse concerns and perspectives in public discourse.

- Several respondents expressed scepticism or outright opposition to the Green Deal, viewing it as detrimental to the economy and citizens. Comments like *"It will destroy the European industry and wealth"* and *"The Green Deal is nothing but a giant tax-grab"* reflected concerns about the policy's impact.
- Some replies contained conspiracy theories or express distrust towards the EU and its agendas, evidenced by comments like "🔥 *These traitors & @WEF / @UN puppets want to destroy Europe*" and *"#ClimateScam."*
- Users also employed irony and sarcasm to criticise the Green Deal, as seen in *"Yes and 1 + 1 = 3"* and *"advantage to industry" 🤡.*
- The responses often had a political or ideological angle, labelling the Green Deal as *"green communist deal"* or *"Corporate Fascism,"* indicating a perceived alignment with broader political or economic ideologies.
- Some users questioned the practicality and feasibility of the Green Deal's initiatives, asking about the replacement of cheaper energy sources with more expensive ones and criticising the lack of environmental assessments for renewable projects.
- Amid the criticisms, there were expressions of support for specific aspects of the Green Deal, such as the hydrogen initiative, showing that not all feedback was negative.
- Comments like *"Nothing else to report? More pressing things going on in Europe"* suggest that some users were seeking more clarity on the EU's priorities and a better understanding of how the Green Deal fits within broader societal concerns.

The feedback on this tweet demonstrates a broad range of opinions, from outright rejection and scepticism to nuanced critiques and selective support. This variety of responses sheds light on the complexity of public reception to policies like the Green Deal and the importance of addressing diverse concerns and perspectives in public discourse.

Figure 19. European Commission's tweet about the European Green Deal

3.2.4 X case study: Public perceptions of clean H₂ in EU policy

A few days later, the European Commission tweeted [advocating for clean hydrogen as a solution for reconciling economic growth with environmental sustainability](#) (Figure 20). The replies were mixed but predominantly critical, with concerns about the credibility, feasibility, and motivations behind the promotion of hydrogen as a clean energy solution. The discussion reflects a broader debate on energy policy, environmental sustainability, and trust in EU leadership and initiatives.

- A substantial number of responses strongly opposed the idea of clean hydrogen, with comments like *"ABSOLUTELY NOT !!!! Clear HYDROGENE is A HUGE LIE !!!"* expressing outright rejection and scepticism toward the initiative.
- Users were inquiring about the source of electricity for hydrogen production, highlighting concerns about the overall sustainability of the hydrogen production process. For example, one user asked, *"And what source of electricity will be used to create this hydrogen?"*
- Several replies criticised the EU's policies and leadership, with comments like *"Ursula von der Leyen should transition to a non-paid job,"* pointing to a lack of trust or approval of the individuals driving these initiatives.
- Some users accused the Commission of spreading misleading information or engaging in scams, as seen in comments like *"It is cheating to talk about 'green deal' with windmills and solar."*
- Amid the criticism, there were expressions of support, such as *"Congratulations for your good work"*.
- The discussion included political and ideological comments that extended beyond hydrogen, indicating that the topic is entangled with broader political sentiments and agendas.
- Some responses used sarcasm or disparaging remarks to express their viewpoint, like *"Madam Faschismus"* or *"You are the dirtiest of all, time to clean your house."*

In summary, the replies to the European Commission's tweet on clean hydrogen were mixed but predominantly critical, with concerns about the credibility, feasibility, and motivations behind the promotion of H₂ as a clean energy solution. The discussion reflects a broader debate on energy policy, environmental sustainability, and trust in EU leadership and initiatives.

Figure 20. European Commission's tweet about clean hydrogen

3.2.5 X case study: The viability of hydrogen fuel cells

A tweet about [hydrogen fuel cell technology's potential](#) was published on 14 October 2023 (Figure 21). The discussion reflects a broad spectrum of opinions on hydrogen fuel cells versus battery technology in green transportation, encompassing concerns about efficiency, infrastructure, environmental impact, and the potential for various applications in different sectors. The following is an analysis of the sentiment and content of the replies:

- Many responses highlighted the substantial energy required to produce hydrogen, emphasising the need for green energy sources. There was interest in tidal energy for its predictability and the potential to produce hydrogen during peak renewable energy generation times.
- There was a clear debate between the efficiency of hydrogen fuel cells versus battery technology. Some users argued that hydrogen production is energy-intensive and less efficient than using electricity directly in batteries.
- Concerns were raised about hydrogen's leaky nature due to its small molecular size, necessitating local production to minimise transportation losses. The difficulty of producing green hydrogen efficiently was also noted.
- Several respondents challenged the notion that battery technology relies heavily on rare metals, pointing out advancements in battery composition that reduce or eliminate the need for such materials.
- Users discussed the lack of investment in hydrogen infrastructure compared to electric vehicles (EVs). There was a sentiment that more focus on hydrogen could have led to different outcomes in green transportation.
- Some comments suggested that hydrogen has potential in sectors like shipping, heavy industry, and long-haul transportation, where battery tech may be less viable.
- The environmental impact of hydrogen production was a concern, with users distinguishing between 'green' hydrogen produced from renewable sources and 'dirty' hydrogen from fossil fuels.
- There were references to international efforts in hydrogen development, with mentions of countries like France and Germany using hydrogen trains and Australia's involvement in hydrogen production.
- Safety concerns related to hydrogen storage and transportation were mentioned, with some users highlighting the risks associated with high-pressure hydrogen storage.
- Opinions varied on the future of hydrogen in transportation, with some advocating for its role alongside batteries, depending on the application, and others sceptical of its viability due to efficiency and infrastructure challenges.

Figure 21. Tweet about hydrogen fuel cell technology

3.2.6 Reddit case study: H₂'s role in the climate crisis

Thread: [Is hydrogen really a clean enough fuel to tackle the climate crisis? “There may be some small role in truly green hydrogen in a decarbonised future, but this is largely a marketing creation by the oil and gas industry that has been hugely overhyped.”](#)

This Reddit thread discusses the viability and efficiency of hydrogen as a clean fuel, focusing on its potential role in addressing the climate crisis. Various users shared diverse perspectives, highlighting the multifaceted nature of the debate on hydrogen energy.

Figure 22. Reddit thread about hydrogen as a clean fuel

The thread features a range of opinions on hydrogen's efficacy as a clean fuel. Some users expressed scepticism about hydrogen's efficiency and practicality, especially in transportation and energy storage, while others saw value in its application in heavy industry and chemical processes. Additionally, many comments raised concerns about hydrogen's energy conversion efficiency. The process of electrolysis, compression, transportation, and utilisation of hydrogen was criticised for its high energy loss compared to direct electricity use or battery storage.

"The problem is that right now it requires more energy input to create hydrogen than energy generated as fuel."

- wilburstiltskin

"The efficiency of storing energy by making hydrogen from electricity and then using it in a fuel cell to make electricity again is about half the efficiency of storing electric energy in a battery and getting it back out of the battery."

- tuctrohs

Several users highlighted the potential of green hydrogen in decarbonising heavy industries such as steelmaking and chemical production. They argued that certain industrial processes cannot be directly electrified and may benefit from hydrogen as a cleaner alternative to fossil fuels. The discussion also includes debates on hydrogen's suitability for light-duty vehicles and residential heating due to efficiency and infrastructure challenges. In this sense, users expressed concerns about the infrastructure required for hydrogen distribution and storage, including issues related to safety, leakage, and the energy-intensive nature of hydrogen compression and transportation.

"Hydrogen is very volatile so has anyone ever seen a hydrogen engine blow up? It's pretty nasty."

- ComprehensiveTax4601

"Storing and burning hydrogen is a waste of energy. Using it in a fuel cell improves things, but again, is wasted energy."

- LordOfRuinsOtherSelf

Throughout the thread, some users suggested that the push for hydrogen could be a form of greenwashing. The discussion reflected a distrust of fossil fuel companies' intentions regarding the promotion of hydrogen energy. Finally, the conversation also touched on the economic aspects of hydrogen production, including subsidies, incentives, and the potential impact of hydrogen on the energy market. Users debated the best allocation of resources and investments in the context of transitioning to cleaner energy sources.

"Green hydrogen is the original clean coal. Same people are promoting it for the same reasons."

- LanternCandle

"Green hydrogen is being promoted because... the model for manufacture, distribution, and sales is the same as the model for petrol fuel."

- gallaj0

3.2.7 Reddit case study: H₂ as a transition fuel

Thread: [Thoughts on Hydrogen Fuel?](#)

The Reddit thread delves into the nuances of hydrogen fuel's role in the transition to cleaner energy, focusing on its potential and limitations. Participants discussed various aspects, including efficiency, production methods, and applications in different sectors.

Figure 23. Reddit thread about hydrogen fuel's role in the transition to cleaner energy

Users expressed doubts about hydrogen's efficiency as an energy carrier. Concerns were highlighted about the energy lost during the conversion process from electricity to hydrogen and back, questioning its practicality compared to direct electric solutions. Users also discussed the potential role of hydrogen in sectors hard to electrify, like heavy transport and industrial processes.

"There is no point transitioning to green hydrogen. It's 3x less efficient than simply transmitting the energy to cars via wires and costs 6x as much."
- almost_not_terrible

"You cannot change the laws of physics to suit your wish for hydrogen to be anything but a niche fuel in the electrified future."
- Initialised

"Heavy transport will be tough and there billions of dollars being invested in that right now."
- Changleen

Throughout the thread, users compared H₂ to batteries and other energy storage methods, discussing the pros and cons. They evaluated hydrogen's role both as a primary energy source and as an energy

carrier or storage mechanism. In addition, concerns were raised about hydrogen's safety due to its volatile nature and the substantial infrastructure investments needed for its storage and distribution.

"Hydrogen is comparable to a battery more than to a fuel."
– Nibb31

"Storing and burning hydrogen is a waste of energy. Using it in a fuel cell improves things, but again, is wasted energy."
– CMG30

Finally, the conversation included economic aspects of hydrogen production and usage, considering costs, subsidies, and the financial feasibility of hydrogen as part of the clean energy transition.

"The main driver to reduce green hydrogen costs is simply electricity costs."
– Changleen

"Grid scale electrolyzers are very expensive so you need to run them as much as possible to get the return on investment."
– CMG30

3.2.8 Reddit case study: H₂'s future in road transport

Thread: ['Far too expensive' | Europe's second-largest truck maker says hydrogen will not be a major road freight fuel. It is about four to five times as costly as what customers are willing to pay. It expects further development in battery technology that will increase the range of heavy-duty EVs.](#)

This thread focuses on the debate over hydrogen's viability as a fuel source for the trucking industry. The main topic revolved around the assertion that hydrogen fuel is considerably more expensive than alternatives, making it an unattractive option for the trucking industry. The thread discussed the cost-effectiveness and efficiency of hydrogen compared to electric vehicles (EVs) and conventional fuels.

Figure 24. Reddit thread about hydrogen's viability as a fuel source for the trucking industry

Some participants argued that when environmental costs are considered, hydrogen—especially when produced via green methods—could be more viable, emphasising the need to factor in the broader environmental impacts of energy choices. There was a consensus that ongoing advancements in battery technology could make electric trucks more competitive, potentially diminishing the role of hydrogen in road freight.

"Yeah hydrogen for cars probably won't be a thing on a large scale commercially. However, for planes, trains and ships it would work great."
 - Laugh92

"It isn't expensive when you start thinking of the environment as a cost."
 - Atheios569

3.2.9 Reddit case study: Viability of hydrogen energy

Thread: [Why the hate on hydrogen?](#)

This thread explores various viewpoints on hydrogen as an energy source. The discussion addressed scepticism around hydrogen, questioning its efficiency and practicality compared to other energy carriers, especially for transportation and home heating.

Figure 25. Reddit thread about hydrogen as an energy source

There were concerns about the suitability of existing infrastructure for hydrogen use and the high costs associated with making necessary modifications. Participants also discussed the economic feasibility and environmental impact of hydrogen, contrasting it with other renewable energy sources and storage methods.

"Hydrogen is just a really bad fuel for any energy purpose... it is very dangerous to handle and thus expensive to use in anything."
- demultipler

"No insurer is going to allow all hydrogen in the home without everything inside the home replaced."
- demultipler

"You can't pay off the cost of hydrogen storage tanks let alone all of the fuel cells on equipment you only use once a year."
- just_one_last_thing

The thread touched on the difference between green, blue, and brown hydrogen, emphasising the importance of sustainable hydrogen production methods. There was also a discussion about the

current state of hydrogen technology, its potential for future development, and the challenges it faces in gaining widespread acceptance.

"There have been a large number of thinly veiled astroturf campaigns where fossil companies pump up the 'hydrogen' portion of 'green hydrogen' while quietly ignoring/denigrating the 'green' part."
 – demultiplexer

"Fuel cells are great but have not proven economical... They are doing better in transport than stationary applications."
 – demultiplexer

3.2.10 Reddit case study: Efficiency and environmental impact of H₂

Thread: [Why the negative sentiment on hydrogen?](#)

This thread dives into the complexities of hydrogen fuel, addressing its potential benefits and substantial challenges. The discussion emphasised the substantial energy required for hydrogen production, particularly through electrolysis, questioning the efficiency of using valuable renewable energy for this purpose.

Figure 26. Reddit thread about the complexities of hydrogen fuel

In addition to the comments related to hydrogen's energy-intensive production, many users explained the difficulties of storing and transporting hydrogen, highlighting its small molecular size, which leads to leakage and the need for high-pressure storage. Participants also discussed the economic viability of H₂ and its environmental impacts, especially when produced from fossil fuels.

*"The amount of energy it takes to perform electrolysis is MASSIVE."
- GalvanicCouple*

*"It's REALLY inefficient compared to just using the electricity directly."
- Ender_A_Wiggin*

*"Storing hydrogen is a BITCH. Hydrogen atoms are so small that they will seep into metal and cause it to embrittle and crack at the microstructural level."
- GalvanicCouple*

Finally, some users suggested that misinformation and vested interests contribute to the promotion of hydrogen, while others argue for a more nuanced understanding.

*"Propaganda would be why. I would guess our rich leaders have money invested in the EV industry."
- Druid__*

*"Hydrogen seems like something that middle-aged men want so that they can insert themselves into the process."
- Revolutionary-Fan235*

*"Because it's mostly about greenwashing by the fossil fuel industry repurposing natural gas into hydrogen."
- Comrade-Porcupine*

3.2.10 Discussion

As shown in the case studies presented above, the nature of X conversations often veered into political or ideological territory. Opinions on H₂ and battery technologies were sometimes influenced by broader political beliefs or scepticism about government policies and industry motivations, indicating that the discussions on this social media platform were both technical and interwoven with users' political stances and perceptions of corporate and governmental agendas.

The discussions reveal a divide in opinions about hydrogen fuel cells as a sustainable transportation solution. While some see substantial potential in H₂, especially when produced from green energy sources, others question its efficiency and practicality compared to battery technology.

A common concern we have identified in social media content was the energy-intensive process required to produce H₂, with many emphasising the need for renewable energy sources to make H₂ a truly green option. There was also a notable perception of a lag in investment and infrastructure

development for hydrogen fuel cells compared to electric vehicles. This issue was seen by some as a barrier to hydrogen's adoption, despite its potential benefits in reducing environmental impact.

In contrast to X posts, Reddit threads displayed a tendency toward more detailed and technical discussions about H₂ and its role in energy systems. While political and ideological perspectives did appear, Reddit discussions tended to be less dominated by political rhetoric compared to X. The emphasis was more on sharing knowledge, asking technical questions, and debating the merits of hydrogen based on scientific and engineering principles rather than political or ideological beliefs.

Similar to X, Reddit users expressed varied opinions on H₂'s viability as a clean energy solution. However, these views were frequently supported by technical arguments, data, or references to studies, giving a more nuanced understanding of the positions presented.

A substantial concern among Reddit users was the overall efficiency of H₂ as an energy carrier. Discussions frequently compared the energy losses in hydrogen production, storage, and usage to direct electricity use, offering detailed explanations of the thermodynamic and engineering challenges. Conversations also explored the potential applications of H₂ in various sectors, with users debating the necessity and feasibility of developing the required infrastructure for H₂, citing specific examples and scenarios where H₂ could be beneficial or problematic.

Many Reddit users focused on the environmental impact of H₂, particularly emphasising the differences between green, blue, and grey hydrogen. Economic aspects, such as the cost of hydrogen production and the implications for industry and consumers, were also thoroughly discussed.

In summary, while there was recognition of H₂'s potential in contributing to a cleaner energy future, the discussions reflected substantial concerns about its current efficiency, infrastructure requirements, economic viability, and environmental impact. The sentiment was that H₂'s role in the energy transition was likely to be niche and application-specific, requiring further technological and economic development to become more broadly viable.

4 Conclusions and implications for public engagement

This analysis offers a panoramic view of how hydrogen technology is discussed on social media across the EU27, revealing patterns of interest, concern, and dialogue. Based on the quantitative and qualitative social media analysis, these are the main conclusions:

- Geographic variability**
 Public interest in hydrogen technology varies substantially across the EU27, with some countries showing high engagement levels, which may correlate with national initiatives or local events related to hydrogen technology.
- Event-driven peaks**
 Public interest in specific hydrogen-related topics appears to be influenced by events, such as industry conferences or government announcements, indicating the public's responsiveness to news and developments in the hydrogen sector.
- Influence of national policies**
 The data suggest that national policies and initiatives, like Greece's National Energy and Climate Plan or Ireland's National Green Hydrogen Strategy, substantially influence public interest in hydrogen technology in those countries.
- Topic-specific interest**
 The level of interest in different aspects of hydrogen technology—such as hydrogen fuel, hydrogen-powered vehicles, and hydrogen infrastructure—varies, indicating divergent public discussions about hydrogen technology within the EU27.
- Technology and mobility interest**
 There is substantial public interest in the technological and mobility aspects of hydrogen, particularly in hydrogen vehicles and fuel cell technology.
- Infrastructure and policy engagement**
 Lower engagement levels on infrastructure and broader policy topics may suggest a gap in public understanding or interest in these areas, highlighting a need for targeted public engagement.
- Socio-political dynamics**
 This analysis highlights the influence of socio-political factors on public perception, with views ranging from scepticism to outright rejection of hydrogen initiatives, particularly when associated with broader political or ideological issues.

Implications for public engagement

Based on our social media analysis, it is recommended that the following be considered for future public engagement efforts focusing on hydrogen technology:

- Develop **region-specific engagement strategies** tailored to each member state's specific interests and concerns, leveraging the data on what aspects of hydrogen technology each population is most engaged with. Ensure that engagement strategies are culturally and linguistically tailored, acknowledging the unique context of each member state to ensure engagement approaches and message content resonate.
- Implement **campaigns to increase public awareness and understanding of hydrogen technology**, its benefits, and its role in the transition to cleaner energy sources. Focus on demystifying the technology and addressing misconceptions, especially in countries with lower engagement levels. Because hydrogen technology is still relatively new as a topic for many people, there is an opportunity to immunise public audiences from likely categories of misinformation, a process known as 'pre-bunking' (debunking before the misinformation arrives with a particular audience member).
- Showcase **local and national success stories and case studies** to demonstrate hydrogen technology's practical benefits and real-world applications, making the technology more relatable and tangible for the public.
- Capitalise on the **interest in hydrogen technology and mobility**, highlighting advancements, real-world applications, and the tangible benefits of hydrogen fuel cell vehicles.
- Enhance **engagement efforts around hydrogen infrastructure and policies**, ensuring these topics are accessible and engaging to a broad audience.
- Leverage **national events, policy announcements, and industry developments** as opportunities to engage the public, providing timely and contextual information that aligns with the public's demonstrated interests.
- Collaborate with **industry stakeholders, academia, and non-governmental organisations** to create a unified message about the benefits and potential of hydrogen technology, amplifying the reach and impact of engagement efforts.
- Continuously **monitor public engagement and sentiment** using tools like Google Trends and social media analysis to adapt strategies in real time, ensuring they remain relevant and responsive to the public's evolving interests and concerns.

By implementing these strategies, the HYPOP project can better align its public engagement activities with the public's perception and interest in hydrogen, fostering a more informed and supportive environment for hydrogen initiatives.

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